

Power Flow-based Estimation of Short-Circuit Currents from Inverter-based Resources

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ABSTRACT The generator side of inverter-based resources (IBRs) interfaced with back-to-back converters is electrically decoupled from the grid. During electrical faults, grid-following IBRs behave as voltage-dependent current sources due to grid code requirements and converter control. This paper presents Newton-Raphson formulations for estimating short-circuit currents from IBRs using novel power flow modeling approaches to address voltage-dependent current sources. The work shows how to represent $dq0$ current injections, which are typically implemented in control architectures based on phase-locked loops. The power flow formulations are adapted to capture grid codes with different characteristics, such as the injection of negative-sequence currents during unbalanced faults. Comparisons against a field-validated electromagnetic transients (EMT) model reveal mean absolute errors of less than 0.5% for the proposed approach when estimating steady-state short-circuit currents from type IV wind turbine generators under grid-following control.

INDEX TERMS Inverter-based resources, Grid codes, Newton-Raphson power flow, Steady-state fault analysis, Voltage-dependent current sources, Wind turbine generators

I. INTRODUCTION

The utilization of renewables has been increasing as the world seeks more sustainable energy alternatives. The Global Wind Energy Council reported that 117 GW of wind power capacity was connected to grids in 2023 [1]. Assets such as type IV wind turbine generators (WTGs), photovoltaic panels, and batteries are often referred to as inverter-based resources (IBRs). The behavior of IBRs during electrical faults differs from that of conventional synchronous generators [2]–[5]. This had a minor impact when IBRs were not widespread. However, this is no longer the case, as the utilization of IBRs in large-scale power systems and microgrids is increasing.

In the context of protection, estimating short-circuit currents (SCC) from energy sources helps avoid issues such as blackouts and equipment damage. Although this is well-established for synchronous generators, grid-following IBRs, especially those fully interfaced by power electronics, require additional attention. As they are asynchronously connected

to the grid due to converters, such IBRs behave as voltage-dependent current sources based on the converter fault-ride-through (FRT) control and grid code (GC) requirements [2]. For context, transmission system operators release GCs to ensure the safe and reliable operation of a grid.

Works such as [3], [4], [6] proposed methods to estimate steady-state SCCs from type IV WTGs. Obtaining the grid's operational state during the fault steady state is a fundamental part of SCC estimation, which involves representing the WTGs as current sources. This can be achieved in different ways. For instance, [3] utilized a Modified Augmented Nodal Analysis algorithm, [4] resorted to sequence equivalents, and [6] adapted the conventional power-based polar Newton-Raphson (PPNR) formulation by adding equations specific to type IV WTGs. Haddadi et al. [7] demonstrated that SCC studies involving IBRs need adequate load modeling for accurate results. In contrast to systems dominated by conventional generators, load currents are comparable to the

fault injections of IBRs due to limitations of the converters. Therefore, load currents should not be neglected as in standard fault analyses. Thus, power flow methods can be a potential path for analyzing faults of IBR-penetrated systems, as they provide flexibility in representing loads in electrical grids.

Although PPNR is more popular in power flow analyses, some studies [8]–[10] claim that current-based rectangular Newton-Raphson (CRNR) formulations computationally outperform PPNR. Da Costa, Martins, and Pereira [8] were the pioneers in proposing CRNR. Apart from utilizing current instead of power mismatches, these were written in rectangular rather than PPNR's polar form. This causes most of the Jacobian matrix to remain unchanged during the iterative process, hence requiring fewer computations. Ever since, CRNR has been further improved [9], [11], [12] and applied to different problems [13]–[16].

This paper's contributions encompass: (i) a $dq0$ -power flow coupling that, as far as the authors know, has not been reported in the literature; (ii) power flow formulations to include voltage-dependent current sources (VDCS) representing grid-following IBRs; (iii) a framework to address unbalanced faults combining PPNR and CRNR with symmetrical components.

Beyond this introduction, Section II revisits power flow formulations and introduces the concept of including current sources. Section III presents the methodology for estimating SCCs from IBRs. Section IV provides the results and discussion. Section V concludes the paper.

II. NEWTON-RAPHSON POWER FLOW METHODS

Power flow calculations are widely used for analyzing electrical grids, with the Newton-Raphson solving method being popular due to its accuracy and quadratic convergence. In such studies, electrical buses are typically modeled as $V\delta$ (slack bus), with unknown active and reactive power generation; PQ , with unknown voltage magnitude and phase; and PV , with unknown voltage phase and reactive power. Note that alternative models exist for specific use cases.

A. POWER-BASED POLAR FORMULATION

Given an electrical grid, PPNR starts with V and δ guesses for PQ buses and δ guesses for PV buses. The guesses are used to calculate active and reactive power for PQ buses and active power for PV buses, which yield mismatches compared to specified values given by generation minus load. PPNR iteratively attempts to nullify the mismatches by updating the guesses using a Jacobian matrix, formed by the partial derivatives of the mismatches. The Jacobian itself is updated in each iteration since the derivatives are functions of V and δ . Once all mismatches are less than a predefined tolerance, steady state is deemed achieved. PPNR writes variables in terms of magnitudes and phases [17], as in:

$$P_k^c = V_k \sum_{i=1}^N Y_{ki} V_i \cos(\delta_k - \theta_{ki} - \delta_i) \quad (1)$$

$$Q_k^c = V_k \sum_{i=1}^N Y_{ki} V_i \sin(\delta_k - \theta_{ki} - \delta_i) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\delta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial V} \\ \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial V} \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} P^s - P^c \\ Q^s - Q^c \end{bmatrix}_h \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ V \end{bmatrix}_{h+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ V \end{bmatrix}_h + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\delta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix}_h, \quad (4)$$

where: P , Q , Y , θ , V , δ , N , and h are the active power, reactive power, admittance matrix magnitude, admittance matrix phase, voltage magnitude, voltage phase, total number of buses, and iteration. Superscripts s and c represent specified and calculated quantities. Subscripts k and i indicate system buses. Matrix quantities with double subscripts denote the row and column indices. Underlined quantities are vectors.

Reference [18] extended PPNR by including buses with constant specified currents and unknown voltage phases and magnitudes, here referred to as type $IaIr$. Equations (5) and (6) calculate currents based on Ohm's Law (neglecting local loads). Equation (7) is the extended formulation. All partial derivatives in the Jacobian depend only on the calculated quantities since the specified power and currents are constants.

$$I_{a_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N Y_{ki} V_i \cos(\theta_{ki} + \delta_i) \quad (5)$$

$$I_{r_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N Y_{ki} V_i \sin(\theta_{ki} + \delta_i) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\delta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial V} \\ \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial V} \\ \frac{\partial I_a^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial I_a^c}{\partial V} \\ \frac{\partial I_r^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial I_r^c}{\partial V} \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} P^s - P^c \\ Q^s - Q^c \\ I_a^s - I_a^c \\ I_r^s - I_r^c \end{bmatrix}_h \quad (7)$$

Upon convergence of the iterative process, the obtained voltage magnitudes and phases define the grid's steady state.

B. CURRENT-BASED RECTANGULAR FORMULATION

In contrast to PPNR, [8] and [12] wrote the equations in rectangular form. Hence, the real (V_a) and imaginary (V_r) parts of the voltage are the variables. The mismatches utilize current equations, with (8) and (9) being the specified currents, whereas (10) and (11) calculate currents according to Ohm's law. In CRNR, the specified currents are not constants as they are functions of V_a and V_r . Thus, derivatives of $I_{a_k}^s$ and $I_{r_k}^s$ are null only for unloaded PQ buses.

$$I_{a_k}^s = (P_k^s V_{a_k} + Q_k^s V_{r_k}) / (V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2) \quad (8)$$

$$I_{r_k}^s = (P_k^s V_{r_k} - Q_k^s V_{a_k}) / (V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2) \quad (9)$$

$$I_{a_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N (G_{ki} V_{a_i} - B_{ki} V_{r_i}) \quad (10)$$

$$I_{r_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N (G_{ki} V_{r_i} + B_{ki} V_{a_i}), \quad (11)$$

where G and B are the real and imaginary parts of Y/θ .

When addressing a PV bus in CRNR, the generated reactive power (Q^g , required for obtaining Q^s) is added as a problem variable, as it is unknown [12]. A third mismatch for each PV bus, as given by (12), aims to meet the specified voltage levels, where V^s is the voltage reference provided to the generator. Each iteration updates Q^g , hence changing Q^s and affecting (8) and (9). The procedure is as in (13) to (15).

$$V_k^s - V_k^c = \Delta V_k, \text{ with } V_k^c = \sqrt{V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta V_a \\ \Delta V_r \\ \Delta Q^g \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{J} & \mathcal{X} \\ \mathcal{Z} & \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} I_r^s - I_r^c \\ I_a^s - I_a^c \\ V^s - V^c \end{bmatrix}_h \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{J} = - \begin{bmatrix} \partial \Delta I_r / \partial V_a & \partial \Delta I_r / \partial V_r \\ \partial \Delta I_a / \partial V_a & \partial \Delta I_a / \partial V_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{X} = - \begin{bmatrix} \partial \Delta I_r / \partial Q^g \\ \partial \Delta I_a / \partial Q^g \end{bmatrix}, \mathcal{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial V^c / \partial V_a & \partial V^c / \partial V_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where $\Delta I_a = I_a^s - I_a^c$ and $\Delta I_r = I_r^s - I_r^c$. \mathcal{J} relates to current mismatches. \mathcal{Z} and \mathcal{X} are the *PV*-related augmentations.

The process updates the variables through (16) and continues until the mismatches are less than a user-defined tolerance.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_r \\ Q^g \end{bmatrix}_{h+1} = \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_r \\ Q^g \end{bmatrix}_h + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta V_a \\ \Delta V_r \\ \Delta Q^g \end{bmatrix}_h, \quad (16)$$

As an advantage over PPNR, only diagonal blocks of \mathcal{J} are susceptible to updates over the iterations since off-diagonal blocks depend solely on Y elements [8], [12]. This paper extends CRNR to include *Ialr* buses. However, the approach for *PV* buses differs from [8], [12]. Furthermore, in contrast to [18], the specified currents of *Ialr* buses are not constants when estimating SCCs. Instead, they are GC- and control-based quantities that require a more complex approach. The upcoming section addresses these aspects.

III. Methods

This section firstly reformulates CRNR's representation of *PV* buses. It then presents the power flow-based methodology for estimating SCCs from IBRs.

A. MODELING PV BUSES IN CRNR

Despite favoring computational efficiency, the *PV* representation from [8], [12] adds new variables (Q^g) and deteriorates the Jacobian condition [19], which may lead to convergence problems. To mitigate these issues, this paper's approach to *PV* buses eliminates current-based mismatches. Given that P is known in *PV* buses, (17) yields one mismatch, with (18) describing the rectangular form of P^c . (12) is the second mismatch, which ensures the voltage magnitude converges to the specified reference. Since (12) and (17) do not depend on Q^g , Jacobian augmentations are not needed.

$$P_k^s - P_k^c = \Delta P_k \quad (17)$$

$$P_k^c = V_{a_k} I_{a_k}^c + V_{r_k} I_{r_k}^c, \quad (18)$$

with $I_{a_k}^c$ and $I_{r_k}^c$ coming from (10) and (11).

This approach causes the off-diagonal *PV*-related elements of \mathcal{J} to change in each iteration, hence requiring more computations than the original CRNR. However, in power flow studies, most buses are typically of type *PQ*. As these follow the original CRNR implementation, the proposed approach still has a significant computational advantage over PPNR, as demonstrated in upcoming sections.

The following subsections focus on linking the power flow methods with IBRs and SCC estimations.

B. VOLTAGE-DEPENDENT CURRENT SOURCES

During electrical faults, grid-following IBRs behave as VDCSs based on the GC and FRT control [2]. When conducting fault analyses using power flow methods, these IBRs should be modeled as *Ialr* buses while in FRT mode. To a limited extent, this is comparable to the work in [18], summarized in subsection A. However, there are two crucial differences: (i) Ohm's Law-based current calculations must follow the $dq0$ frame to adequately represent the IBR's phase-locked loop (PLL); (ii) when estimating SCCs from IBRs, I_a^s and I_r^s are GC-based functions that describe the voltage dependency rather than being constant quantities.

Regarding item (i), i.e., the current calculations based on Ohm's law (I_a^c and I_r^c), one crucial aspect arises when analyzing IBRs. The control architecture of grid-following IBRs usually employs a PLL whose inputs are in the $dq0$ rather than the abc frame [2]. Aligning the currents to the d and q axes requires the currents to be quantified in the $dq0$ frame. In a PLL-based control referring to bus k , when the currents align with the d and q axes, it is true that

$$P_k + jQ_k = \dot{V}_k \cdot \dot{I}_k^* = V_k \cdot \left(\dot{I}_k^{dq0} \right)^*, \quad (19)$$

with \dot{I}_k^{dq0} being the $dq0$ current.

Dividing (19) by V_k :

$$1/\delta_k \cdot (I_{a_k}^c - jI_{r_k}^c) = I_{a_k}^{dq0} - jI_{r_k}^{dq0} \quad (20)$$

In polar form, (20) implies:

$$I_{a_k}^{dq0} = I_{a_k}^c \cos \delta + I_{r_k}^c \sin \delta \quad (21)$$

$$I_{r_k}^{dq0} = I_{r_k}^c \cos \delta - I_{a_k}^c \sin \delta, \quad (22)$$

with $I_{a_k}^c$ and $I_{r_k}^c$ coming from (5) and (6).

In rectangular form, (20) leads to:

$$I_{a_k}^{dq0} = (I_{a_k}^c V_{a_k} + I_{r_k}^c V_r) / \sqrt{V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2} \quad (23)$$

$$I_{r_k}^{dq0} = (I_{r_k}^c V_{a_k} - I_{a_k}^c V_r) / \sqrt{V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2}, \quad (24)$$

with $I_{a_k}^c$ and $I_{r_k}^c$ coming from (10) and (11)

Based on the $dq0$ control, (25) represents the mismatches for type *Ialr* buses representing IBRs in FRT mode.

$$I_{a_k}^s - I_{a_k}^{dq0} = \Delta I_{a_k}^*, I_{r_k}^s - I_{r_k}^{dq0} = \Delta I_{r_k}^* \quad (25)$$

Note that other PLL structures, e.g., based on the $\alpha\beta$ frame, could be used. These would require modifying (19) to (24).

Concerning item (ii) in the first paragraph of this subsection, the FRT behavior of grid-following IBRs can be generically written as in the GC-based (26) to (30). Priority is given to reactive currents, as in many GCs that aim to provide voltage support to the grid during faults [2].

$$I_r^+ = -K_f^+ \cdot (V_C - V_{res}^+ - D_b) + \gamma \cdot I_{r_{pf}}^+ \quad (26)$$

$$I_r^- = 0 \text{ or } |I_r^-| = K_f^- \cdot V_{res}^- \quad (27)$$

$$|I_r^+| \leq 1 \text{ p.u.} \quad (28)$$

$$P^g \leq P_{pf} \quad (29)$$

$$\sqrt{(I_a^+)^2 + (I_r^+)^2} + |I_r^-| \leq I_M, \quad (30)$$

where + and - indicate positive- and negative-sequence quantities; K_f is the proportional gain of the converter controller; V_C is a GC-dependent voltage quantity (nominal or pre-fault); V_{res} is the IBR's residual voltage; D_b is a deadband; the pf subscript denotes pre-fault quantities; $\gamma \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates a pre-fault reactive current summation; I_M is the magnitude of the converter's maximum FRT current.

Equation (27) dictates if there should be negative-sequence reactive injections during FRT. The sign of I_r^- depends on the fault type, as explained in the next subsection. Sparing a share of I_M for active injection helps preserve the converter [2]. Assuming that $I_M > 1$, (28) leaves room for active currents if $|I_r^+|$ tends to surpass 1 p.u. (29) states that the generated power in FRT is less than or equal to the pre-fault power reference. (30) limits the overall injection according to I_M .

In SCC estimations concerning IBRs, the GC sets the specified currents for (25). For instance, assume an electrical grid where an IBR's positive and negative sequences are represented by buses k and i , respectively. Then, $I_{r_k}^s$ is either given by (26)'s I_r^+ , where $V_{res}^+ = V_k$, or by (28)'s unity in case of saturation. If the GC enables negative-sequence injections, $I_{r_i}^s$ comes from (27)'s I_r^- , where V_{res}^- depends on the fault type, as clarified in the following subsection. If IBR k can supply P_{pf} while complying with (26) and (27), then

$$I_{a_k}^s = P_{pf}/V_k, \quad (31)$$

i.e., the $dq0$ active current based on the pre-fault power reference and the IBR's positive-sequence voltage (a variable changing in each Newton-Raphson iteration). If complying with (26) and (27) implies the IBR cannot meet P_{pf} , its active injection depends on how much is left of I_M given the positive- and negative-sequence reactive injections. In such a case, $I_{a_k}^s$ comes from (30)'s I_a^+ . Implementation-wise, each Newton-Raphson iteration first obtains $I_{a_k}^s$ based on (30). If $I_{a_k}^s \cdot V_k > P_{pf}$, the specification changes to (31). In every iteration, if the specification follows (31) but (30) yields a current that implies $P < P_{pf}$, the specification changes back to (30). Note that $I_{a_i}^s$ is always null, as there are no negative-sequence active currents during a fault steady state.

Given the VDCS, PLL, and GC discussions, this paper's final polar form Newton-Raphson formulation is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\delta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial V} \\ \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q^c}{\partial V} \\ -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r^*}{\partial \delta} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r^*}{\partial V} \\ -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a^*}{\partial \delta} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a^*}{\partial V} \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} P^s - P^c \\ Q^s - Q^c \\ I_r^s - I_r^{dq0} \\ I_a^s - I_a^{dq0} \end{bmatrix}_h, \quad (32)$$

where: $P^s - P^c$ relate to PQ and PV buses; $Q^s - Q^c$ relate to PQ buses; $I_a^s - I_a^{dq0}$, $I_r^s - I_r^{dq0}$ relate to $IaIr$ buses.

Equation (33) shows the final rectangular formulation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta V_a \\ \Delta V_r \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r}{\partial V_a} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r}{\partial V_r} \\ -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a}{\partial V_a} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a}{\partial V_r} \\ -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r^*}{\partial V_a} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_r^*}{\partial V_r} \\ -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a^*}{\partial V_a} & -\frac{\partial \Delta I_a^*}{\partial V_r} \\ \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial V_a} & \frac{\partial P^c}{\partial V_r} \\ \frac{\partial V^c}{\partial V_a} & \frac{\partial V^c}{\partial V_r} \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} I_r^s - I_r^c \\ I_a^s - I_a^c \\ I_r^s - I_r^{dq0} \\ I_a^s - I_a^{dq0} \\ P^s - P^c \\ V^s - V^c \end{bmatrix}_h, \quad (33)$$

where: $I_r^s - I_r^c$, $I_a^s - I_a^c$ relate to PQ buses; $I_r^s - I_r^{dq0}$, $I_a^s - I_a^{dq0}$ relate to $IaIr$ buses; $P^s - P^c$, $V^s - V^c$ relate to PV buses.

With the formulations in place, the following steps outline the circuit modeling approaches based on the fault type.

C. FAULT CIRCUITS

This paper addresses three-line-to-ground (TLG), line-to-line (LL), and one-line-to-ground (LG) faults through the theory of symmetrical components [20], [21]. The analyzed IBR is a type IV WTG, which connects to a Thevenin equivalent grid, as in Fig. 1, where z_{fi} , z_{bt} and z_{fa} are the WTG filter, WTG transformer-busbar, and fault impedances. In normal conditions, the WTG behaves as a PV bus as it follows active power and voltage references. To facilitate explanations, the buses are numbered in Fig. 1 and other circuit figures. Subsection D provides information on the impedances.

FIGURE 1. Single-generator system at pre-fault conditions.

The system's FRT circuit depends on the fault type since each type implies a different way of combining the sequence components [21] and interpreting (26) to (30).

In TLG faults, only the positive sequence is relevant during steady state. A dummy PQ (bus 4) represents the fault point, which is grounded through the fault impedance, as in Fig. 2, where $f_{loc} \in [0, 1]$ sets the fault location by splitting z_{th} . The VDCS modeling the WTG is an $IaIr$ bus. For TLG faults and any other fault type, $V_{res}^+ = V_1$.

Pos. seq. during-fault circuit

FIGURE 2. Circuit model for TLG faults.

In LL faults, the positive and negative sequences connect in parallel by linking the sequence fault points (buses 4 and 7) through the fault impedance, as in Fig. 3. If negative-sequence injection is not in the GC, bus 5 is replaced with an unloaded PQ bus. Concerning (27), I_r^- is positive in LL faults since the positive- and negative-sequence currents flow in the opposite directions. As a reminder, the positive-sequence reactive current is intended to be inductive (less than zero), as shown in (26). Negative-sequence voltages originate directly from the negative-sequence buses [21], thus $V_{res}^- = V_5$.

In LG faults, all sequence circuits connect in series with thrice the fault impedance. The negative-sequence injection comes from the positive-sequence fault point, as in Fig. 4(a). To represent this aspect, this paper adds a dummy VDCS

FIGURE 3. Circuit model for LL faults.

at the positive-sequence fault point, which injects the same current magnitude as the negative-sequence VDCS but with the opposite sign, as in Fig. 4(b).

FIGURE 4. a) Negative-sequence injection in LG faults; b) Power flow equivalent model.

Fig. 5 shows the circuit for LG faults. No zero-sequence currents flow on the WTG since the transformer has a grounded-star-to-delta connection. No currents reach the PQ bus on the left-hand side of $f_{loc}z_{th}^0$ since this impedance is on an open path. If the GC does not impose negative-sequence injection, unloaded PQ buses replace the VDCSs in buses 5 and 4. In addition, Z_{fi} links to bus 4 instead of being grounded. When computing (27), I_r^- is negative in LG fault

FIGURE 5. Circuit model for LG faults.

circuits, as the positive and negative-sequence currents flow in the same direction.

In (27), since $I_{r5}^s = -K_f^- V_{res}^-$, Fig. 4 implies $I_{r4}^s = K_f^- V_{res}^-$. The magnitude of the WTG's negative-sequence voltage is

$$V_{res}^- = |V_5/\delta_5 - V_4/\delta_4|, \quad (34)$$

whose polar and rectangular forms are:

$$V_{res}^- = \sqrt{(V_5 \cos \delta_5 - V_4 \cos \delta_4)^2 + (V_5 \sin \delta_5 - V_4 \sin \delta_4)^2} \quad (35)$$

$$V_{res}^- = \sqrt{(V_{a5} - V_{a4})^2 + (V_{r5} - V_{r4})^2}. \quad (36)$$

As a remark, the approach presented in Fig. 4(b) and reflected in Fig. 5 is merely an artifice to model the negative-sequence injection. Although bus 5 is grounded in Fig. 5, the negative-sequence voltage must be calculated as in (34). For the same reason, bus 4's injection does not impact the converter capacity as it is a dummy bus.

D. FRAMEWORK FOR SCC ESTIMATIONS

So far, this section has addressed the inclusion of GCs and PLL-based grid-following WTGs in power flow studies according to various fault types. These aspects are the core of the proposed approach, summarized in Fig. 6.

FIGURE 6. Flowchart of the proposed methodology.

After computing the required information, if V_C is not the nominal voltage or $\gamma = 1$ in (26), a pre-fault power flow yields the IBR's V_{pf} and $I_{rpf}^+ = -Q_{pf}^g/V_{pf}$. Then, one needs to calculate the Y matrix according to the fault type, based on Figs. 2, 3, and 5. Lastly, the Newton-Raphson formulations in (32) and (33) estimate the FRT steady states.

In the FRT context, IBR manufacturers can implement additional strategies to ensure the adequate operation of the IBR. For instance, during unbalanced faults, following GCs that do not enable negative-sequence injection can lead the IBR to FRT scenarios where the healthy phase(s) voltage surpasses the upper limit. In other words, strictly following the GC would trigger the over-voltage protection. In such scenarios, it is valid to decrease the magnitude of the IBR reactive injection so that the healthy phase voltage is within the operational bounds. As another example, if the GC imposes negative-sequence injections, there may be scenarios where the overall required injection exceeds I_M . Although such currents must be decreased to secure feasible injections, to the authors' knowledge, the procedure for balancing the decrements between positive and negative injections has not

been standardized. Thus, different manufacturers may address such occasions in distinct ways. This paper cannot disclose the strategies utilized to circumvent such challenges, as this would violate intellectual property. However, the following section presents results and provides instructions for replicating cases that do not rely on any manufacturer-specific strategy.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed power flow algorithms in estimating steady-state SCCs from grid-following type IV WTGs. This is achieved by including VDCSs (*Ialr* buses) in PPNR and CRNR to conduct fault analyses during both balanced and unbalanced faults. Although this research utilizes WTGs as converter-based power sources, note that any grid-following IBR subjected to GCs can be analyzed through the proposed approach.

A. VALIDATING THE ESTIMATION METHOD

This paper's industrial EMT model representing the type IV WTG was developed in PSCADTM. It has been validated through comparisons with real measurements of FRT events, in accordance with various GCs and standards, such as IEC 61400-21-1 [22]. Aerodynamic and shaft models define the mechanical system. The electrical part includes the permanent magnet synchronous generator, back-to-back converter, DC link, grid-side converter reactor, filter, WTG transformer with saturation and frequency-dependent impedance, and measurement ports. The control system comprises the WTG level controller, which features reduced-order characteristics necessary for EMT simulations. Moreover, it includes the actual grid-following converter controller (which manages the generator- and grid-side converters) and the DC link. The model contains the full-order real converter control and protection codes embedded as a *.dll* file.

Fig. 7 illustrates the grid-following control utilized in this paper's EMT simulations. A PLL synchronizes with the grid's frequency and yields phase references for *abc-dq0* transformations. The wind power plant (WPP) controller sends power or voltage references to the outer voltage/power control loop, which calculates the *dq0* reference currents for current control. During an FRT event, the FRT control takes charge and defines the *dq0* reference currents, according to pre- and during-fault measurements and grid code requirements. The total current is then capped at the equipment's limit and passed to the fast inner current control loop, which yields voltage references to the pulse-width modulator (PWM). The scheme can be based either on coupled sequence control or decoupled sequence control. The latter is used in this paper.

Before applying the fault in PSCAD, the WTG was started and reached a steady state. Then, EMT simulations occurred with a time-step lower than 10 μs and 5 kHz sampling rate to save the data. Sequence components were calculated using full-cycle windows (20 ms for 50 Hz) and a 2 kHz sampling rate. To increase the likelihood of an FRT steady state, the faults were cleared 4000 ms after their occurrence, and all

FIGURE 7. Topology of the grid-following control (grid side) [2] (adapted).

protection was deactivated. Steady-state currents and voltages were measured as the average values over the last 100 ms of the fault. Although the faults would be cleared in a shorter time in actual FRT events, the purpose of this paper is to validate the proposed methods. The power flow codes were implemented in MATLAB R2022a, and executed in a 64 GB RAM, Intel[®] Core[™] i9-11950H 2.6 GHz workstation.

Calculations for Fig 1's z_{th} and z_{fa} , in p.u., are:

$$z_{th} = SCR^{-1}, z_{fa} = V_{ret} \cdot z_{th} \cdot (1 - f_{loc}) / (1 - V_{ret}), \quad (37)$$

where R_{fa} , R_{th} , X_{fa} and X_{th} are calculated according to:

$$R = Z / \sqrt{1 + (XR_{ratio})^2}, X = \sqrt{Z^2 - R^2} \quad (38)$$

The SCC estimations in this paper are based on two real GCs, with parameters in Table 1. GC 1 includes a deadband and takes $V_C = V_{pf}$ instead of the nominal voltage. GC 2 enables negative-sequence injection. Both add I_{rpf}^+ in (26).

TABLE 1. Parameters for the grid codes under study

	K_f^+	K_f^-	V_C	D_b	γ
GC 1	2	0	Pre-fault	0.1	1
GC 2	2	2	Nominal	0	1

The EMT simulations and Newton-Raphson estimations considered all combinations of Table 2's parameters. The slack bus voltage (V_{sys}) is 1 p.u. in all cases. Table 2 yields 24 different combinations, which are simulated for each fault type and GC, resulting in a total of 144 different cases.

Due to confidentiality, z_{fi} and z_{bt} cannot be disclosed. Nonetheless, replication instructions are presented further ahead. The Newton-Raphson convergence tolerance was set

TABLE 2. Inputs to generate cases for EMT simulations and steady-state SCC estimations, with I_M , V_{pf} , P_{pf} and V_{ret} in p.u.

I_M	V_{pf}	SCR	P_{pf}	V_{ret}	f_{loc}	XR_{ratio}
1.11	1	3, 6	0.1, 1	0.01, 0.2	0.01, 0.5, 0.95	15

to 10^{-4} . Although smart initialization could be employed, voltage and phase variables were initialized as 1 p.u. and 0 rad to ensure unbiased simulations. Figs. 8 and 9 compare the power flow SCC estimations with the EMT results. The results refer to PPNR and CRNR, as both achieved identical

equilibrium points. The plots for I_r^+ flip the y axis since such currents are inductive. Only Fig. 9 shows I_r^- since GC 1 does not enable such injections. These currents are presented as absolute values, as their signs depend on the fault type.

Several TLG fault cases have not converged (indicated by the absence of a + symbol in Figs. 8 and 9). Except for cases 23 and 95, all non-converged cases relate to TLG bolted faults ($V_{ret} = 0.01$). Severe TLG faults pose limitations on the currents the WTG can transfer to the fault, as they tend to isolate the WTG from the grid, especially for distant faults. Since the currents cannot flow into the network, the WTG tends to become unstable if the fault is not cleared fast enough.

FIGURE 8. Grid code 1: power flow estimations (+) against EMT results (x). Fault types: $\square \rightarrow$ TLG, $\square \rightarrow$ LL, $\square \rightarrow$ LG. The x-axis indicates the cases.

FIGURE 9. Grid code 2: power flow estimations (+) against EMT results (x). Fault types: $\square \rightarrow$ TLG, $\square \rightarrow$ LL, $\square \rightarrow$ LG. The x-axis indicates the cases.

Cases 23 and 95 concern fault scenarios with $SCR = 3$, i.e., a relatively weak grid, distant faults ($f_{loc} = 0.95$), and full injection from the converter since $P_{pf} = 1$ p.u. This combination with a long fault duration led to instability.

Time-domain EMT observations confirmed that all non-converged power flow cases also failed to reach equilibrium points in PSCAD. Hence, the EMT results for such cases in Figs. 8 and 9 do not reflect steady-state conditions. They are merely the average of the quantities during the last 100 ms of the unstable FRT behavior. Fig. 10 shows the EMT results for Fig. 8's case 1, demonstrating the failure in achieving a steady state in EMT. As a remark, the non-null negative-sequence voltages in the EMT results for balanced faults further indicate the lack of true steady states.

FIGURE 10. EMT electrical quantities for case 1, which show the lack of an equilibrium point. The gray area indicates the last 100 ms of the fault.

Regarding the absence of convergence in some cases, it is emphasized that all protection was deactivated in the EMT simulations to increase the likelihood of achieving FRT steady states, if an equilibrium point is feasible. In real scenarios where such a point does not exist, the WTG would either ride through the fault after its clearance, or protection would be triggered. The IEEE 2800-2022 standard [23] provides suggestions for better FRT responses from IBRs during severe faults. However, such aspects relate to dynamic behaviors that are beyond the scope of this work.

Subsection B stated that the WTG's active injection depends on the feasibility of delivering P_{pf} during the fault. In Fig. 8, cases with $P_{pf} = 0.1$ p.u. are identifiable through their active currents around 0.15 p.u. For instance, in case 49, $I_a^+ \approx 0.13$ p.u. and $I_r^+ \approx 0.26$ p.u., resulting in an overall injection of 0.29 p.u., i.e., significantly below I_M . That is because such an active current combined with $V^+ \approx 0.77$ p.u. leads to the P_{pf} input of 0.1 p.u. Thus, the VDCS certainly followed (31) as specified active current prior to convergence. Case 51, which differs from case 49 only in terms of $P_{pf} = 1$ p.u., fully utilizes the converter's current capacity.

Table 3 shows the mean absolute errors (*MAE*) for all converged cases, revealing accurate matches between the power flow-based SCC estimations and the EMT results.

TABLE 3. Steady-state SCC estimation errors (%) against the EMT results

	V^+	δ^+	V^-	I_a^+	$ I_r^+ $	$ I_r^- $
<i>MAE</i>	0.058	0.333	0.094	0.441	0.267	0.422

Along z_{fi} and z_{bt} , subsection D mentioned confidential strategies that could compromise the replicability of the presented results. Table 4 provides parameters for cases that are independent of any such strategies. In these cases, $V_{pf} = 1$ p.u., $XR_{ratio} = 15$, and z_{fi} and z_{bt} were set to $-j100$ and $j0.1$, respectively, to yield the simplified results in Table 5, thereby enabling replication and validation.

TABLE 4. Cases for replication and validation: parameters.

Case	P_{pf} (p.u.)	SCR	f_{loc}	V_{ret} (p.u.)	Fault type	GC
5	0.1	3	0.01	0.2	TLG	1
16	1	6	0.5	0.2	TLG	1
109	0.1	3	0.5	0.2	LL	2
119	1	3	0.95	0.2	LL	2
121	0.1	3	0.01	0.01	LG	2
144	1	6	0.95	0.2	LG	2

TABLE 5. Cases for replication and validation: simplified results (p.u.).

Case	V^+	δ^+	V^-	I_a^+	I_r^+	$ I_r^- $
5	0.367	41.675°	0	0.267	1.004	0
16	0.383	56.603°	0	0.482	1.004	0
109	0.749	34.138°	0.251	0.133	0.496	0.499
119	0.814	45.894°	0.218	0.411	0.542	0.434
121	0.769	33.316°	0.230	0.130	0.456	0.458
144	0.833	42.924°	0.174	0.638	0.425	0.346

B. COMPUTATIONAL EFFORT ANALYSIS

Although this paper focuses on SCC estimations, part of the research involves proposing the use of CRNR over PPNR. Table 6 provides the average time/iteration required by PPNR and CRNR, disregarding the non-converged cases. The fault type has a significant impact on convergence time due to the size of the FRT circuit. As illustrated in Figs. 2, 3, and 5, TLG, LL, and LG faults yield circuits with 4, 7, and 8 buses, respectively, for the system under study. Larger models naturally require more computation time.

TABLE 6. Mean time per iteration (ms) based on 100 executions

	CRNR			PPNR		
	TLG	LL	LG	TLG	LL	LG
GC 1	0.0423	0.0631	0.0708	0.0933	0.1782	0.2124
GC 2	0.0434	0.0841	0.0829	0.0921	0.1974	0.2220

There was a large discrepancy between PPNR and CRNR, with the time/iteration from the former to the latter decreasing by around 55 to 65% across the different fault types.

Fig. 11 shows the number of iterations in each case. CRNR and PPNR reached 100 iterations in most of the non-converged cases, achieving “NaN” elements in intermediary iterations due to poorly conditioned Jacobians in a few of the

cases. Excluding the non-converged cases, CRNR and PPNR required averages of 5.21 and 7.44 iterations, respectively. Combined with the previous time/iteration analysis, these numbers suggest that CRNR can significantly outperform PPNR computationally, requiring fewer iterations to converge (on average) and taking less time to compute each iteration.

FIGURE 11. Number of iterations. The x-axis indicates the cases.

C. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS FOR LARGE SYSTEMS

The system in Fig. 1 is sufficient for validating WTG-level responses. However, convergence can be a concern when using power flow to analyze faults in large systems. Therefore, it is essential to recognize the limitations of this approach.

The proposed CRNR and PPNR algorithms were applied to the IEEE 14, 30, 57, 118, and 300 bus systems [24]. Type IV WTGs replaced part of the generators in those systems. Faults were simulated close to the WTGs to ensure they would enter FRT mode. Table 7 shows the case sets, where “WTG buses” indicate which buses were replaced, hence indirectly showing how many WTGs are in the case set. The sets were subjected to the three discussed fault types, which were applied between the buses indicated under “fault point”. The cases were tagged based on the fault type and the case set, e.g., TLG2, LL7, or LG9.

When replacing a generator with a WTG, local loads were neglected, as loads do not usually connect directly to a WTG’s busbar. The original generator bus was removed and replaced with the WTG and its busbar, as shown in Fig. 12. Since there is no transformer information in [24], none was assumed to cause isolation in the zero-sequence circuit, except for the ones from the WTGs. In addition,

FIGURE 12. Replacement of a conventional generator with a WTG.

negative- and zero-sequence impedances were taken as equal to the positive-sequence ones. References for conventional generators were kept as in [24]. In all cases, z_{fa} , z_{fi} and z_{bt} are equal to 0.005, $-j100$ and $j0.1$ p.u., respectively. The power base was set at 14 MW. Since [24]’s base is 100 MW, all impedances were adjusted. No manufacturer-specific strategy was applied, hence enabling full replication.

Table 8 shows the number of iterations and the average time/iteration across 100 executions. No results are shown for the IEEE 300-bus system, as both CRNR and PPNR diverged in that system. Several parameter combinations were attempted, but with no success. Such results suggest a potential feasibility limitation regarding the size of systems that the proposed power flow-based SCC approach can address. As an observation, Table 8 corroborates the previous subsection by showing CRNR’s computational advantage over PPNR, especially for asymmetrical faults.

Fig. 13 presents the electrical quantities regarding the cases. For readers replicating the method, it is recommended to use an image data extraction tool for retrieving results. Some noticeable remarks concerning Fig. 13: (i) WTG 2 in case LG6 saturated its reactive injection ($I_r^+ \approx -1$ p.u.). Given its $I_{r_{pf}}^+ = -0.326$ p.u., $V_C = V_{pf} = 1.005$ p.u., and FRT voltage of 0.536 p.u., plugging these values into (26) yields $I_r^+ = -1.064$, so the algorithm holds I_r^+ at -1 p.u.; (ii) among the case sets that enable negative-sequence injections through GC 2, no WTG injected I_r^- in case LG7 since the negative-sequence voltages were null in steady state, meaning that (27) yielded zero; (iii) as expected, cases sets with relatively low P_{pf} did not fully utilize the converter’s

TABLE 7. Simulation cases for convergence analysis

Case set	IEEE system	P_{pf} (p.u.)	f_{loc}	Grid code	WTG buses	Fault point
1	14	0.8	0.3	2	2, 3	2, 4
2	14	0.5	0.8	1	3, 6	3, 4
3	30	1	0.9	2	5, 8	5, 7
4	30	0.2	0.1	1	2, 5	2, 5
5	57	1	0.2	2	9, 12	9, 13
6	57	0.6	0.5	1	6, 8, 9	6, 8
7	118	0.7	0.6	2	89, 90, 91	89, 90
8	118	0.5	0.9	1	103, 104, 105	103, 104
9	300	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 8. Iterations for convergence and mean time per iteration (ms)

Case set	Iterations (CRNR, PPNR)			Time per iteration (CRNR, PPNR)		
	TLG	LL	LG	TLG	LL	LG
1	5, 6	4, 9	4, 8	0.1, 0.5	0.4, 1.0	0.8, 1.7
2	5, 6	4, 10	4, 9	0.2, 0.4	0.5, 0.9	0.6, 1.4
3	4, 7	4, 11	6, 10	0.3, 0.9	1.5, 2.6	2.7, 4.2
4	5, 6	4, 10	4, 6	0.4, 0.9	1.4, 2.8	2.1, 4.0
5	5, 6	4, 11	6, 12	1.3, 2.3	4.7, 5.9	6.9, 11.4
6	6, 7	4, 12	6, 11	0.9, 2.5	3.8, 6.3	6.6, 10.8
7	8, 6	6, 12	16, 16	2.7, 7.3	11.1, 13.9	20.1, 23.1
8	7, 6	5, 12	14, 14	3.2, 7.7	10.7, 13.6	19.9, 22.5

FIGURE 13. FRT simulations of the IEEE bus systems.

capacity. For instance, $V^+ \approx 0.789$ p.u. and $I_a^+ \approx 0.634$ p.u. for WTG 1 in case TLG8, whose multiplication yields the pre-fault power reference of 0.5 p.u. Given its $I_r^+ \approx 0.230$ p.u., the total current magnitude is ≈ 0.674 p.u. (below $I_M = 1.11$ p.u.); (iv) in cases LG4 and LL8, WTGs 2 and 3 inject capacitive currents $I_r^+ \approx 0.053$ and 0.071 p.u., respectively. Such occurrences are counterintuitive since the purpose of providing grid support during FRT events is not fulfilled. The reason for such injections comes from the GCs, which add $I_{r_{pf}}^+$ to the FRT injection. In cases LG4 and LL8, the pre-fault injection is capacitive due to the overall grid conditions. This ultimately results in the WTGs not providing the intended voltage support. Occurrences such as these have been under discussion among transmission system operators. Some propose that $I_{r_{pf}}^+$ be added to the FRT current only if it is reactive, thereby avoiding such incidents. As an observation, executing cases LG4 and LL8 with $\gamma = 0$ yields FRT reactive injections of ≈ -0.040 and -0.102 p.u. for WTGs 2 and 3. This demonstrates that the $I_{r_{pf}}^+$ summation is not beneficial in these cases.

Despite diverging in the IEEE 300-bus system, the authors argue that convergence in the 118-bus and smaller systems demonstrates the value of the proposed power flow-based approach for analyzing faults in diverse electrical grids penetrated by IBRs. This statement is supported by the validated estimations reported in subsection A.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed power flow methods for SCC studies involving IBRs. A $dq0$ current formulation captured the FRT behavior of grid-following type IV WTGs. The results indicated that the approach can effectively address GCs with varying characteristics, including negative-sequence injection. Comparisons with a field-validated EMT model yielded mean absolute errors of less than 0.5% when estimating steady-state FRT voltages and currents. Regarding the algorithms, this paper's findings suggest that CRNR is more suitable than PPNR for large-scale simulations. For the conducted studies, the former required less time per iteration and, in most cases, fewer iterations. Convergence tests were successful in IEEE systems with up to 118 buses, demonstrating the applicability of the proposed approach.

The continuation of this work regards implementing strategies to enhance the algorithm's robustness, potentially enabling convergence in the IEEE 300-bus system and other larger systems. Furthermore, future work on this topic is meant to (i) discuss with short-circuit software developers and assess the possibility of incorporating the developed methods into fault analysis computational tools (ii) estimate steady-state SCCs from grid-forming IBRs, (iii) assess the possibility of incorporating PLL freeze to the proposed method as a means for analyzing severe faults, (iv) investigate in which conditions and to which extent the number of WTGs can impact convergence when analyzing faults through the proposed approach, (v) carry out a sensitivity analysis concerning the converter parameters and the impact on the steady-state estimations and (vi) conduct in-depth studies on potential convergence problems in SCC estimations according to different grid aspects, such as a very low SCR or a high fault impedance. The former can lead to the absence of equilibrium points. When the latter is high, challenges arise since protection may not detect the fault.

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